

Molecular Rearrangements of D:A-Friedoolean-6 α ,7 α -epoxide

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A number of interesting cases of epoxide ring opening followed by molecular rearrangements have been reported¹. The earlier studies on the molecular rearrangements of some pentacyclic triterpenoids² prompted us to investigate the molecular rearrangements of D:A-friedoolean-6 α ,7 α -epoxide (1).

The epoxide (1) was prepared from epi-putranjivone (2) whose tosyl derivative (3) gave isoputranjivene (4) by lithium aluminium hydride in tetrahydrofuran. The nmr spectrum of 4 showed singlets at δ 0.80 (3H), 0.81 (3H), 0.91 (3H), 0.96 (3H), 1.04 (3H), 1.09 (3H), 1.28 (3H) for the seven tertiary methyl groups and a doublet (3H) at δ 1.16 (J 3 Hz) for the secondary methyl group at C-4. Signal for the olefinic proton at C-6 appeared as a triplet (1H) at δ 5.3 and that for the olefinic proton at C-7 appeared as an ill-defined multiplet (1H) centered around δ 5.6.

Isoputranjivene (4) on treatment with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid yielded two epoxides. The major product (ca. 76% yield) was assumed, from steric considerations, as D:A-friedoolean-6 α ,7 α -epoxide (1), and the minor product as D:A-friedoolean-6 β ,7 β -epoxide (5). These two epoxides differ significantly in respect to their nmr spectra. The nmr spectrum of 1 showed ill-defined multiplet (2H) at δ 3.34 due to the protons at C-6 and C-7 whereas in 5, proton at C-6 appeared as doublet (1H) at δ 2.98 (J 4 Hz) and the proton at C-7 appeared as a pair of doublets (1H) centered at δ 3.08 (J 2 Hz, 3 Hz). Mass spectra (see Experimental) of both the epoxides revealed fragmentation patterns in conformity with those of friedelane class of pentacyclic triterpenoids³⁻⁵.

Treatment of the epoxide (1) with dry hydrogen chloride gas in chloroform gave the hitherto unknown non-conjugated diene (6). The nmr spectrum of 6 showed singlets at δ 0.84 (3H), 0.88 (3H), 0.99 (6H), 1.1 (3H) and 1.18 (3H) due to the six tertiary methyl groups. Doublets at δ 0.92 (3H, J 3 Hz) and 1.6 (3H, J 3 Hz) appeared for the two secondary methyl groups. Signal for the olefinic proton at C-15 appeared as a pair of doublets (1H) at δ 5.5 (J 2 Hz, 3 Hz). The mass spectrum (Chart 1) of 6 was more diagnostic which revealed the molecular ion peak at m/z 408 (M^+ , 22%). The fragment (a) appeared as base peak at m/z 284 which was expected to be formed by the retro-Diels-Alder fragmentation of ring-D like olean-12-enes⁵. The prominent fragments b, c, d and e were at m/z 258 (48%), 190 (7%), 189 (92%) and 124 (22%) respectively. The mass fragmentation pattern was thus in excellent conformity with the proposed structure (6) for the diene.

Chart 1. Some mass spectral fragments of compound (6).

$\text{C}_7\text{-O}$ (α) bond scission in 7 takes place with the probable formation of a classical carbocation⁶ (8) which undergoes hydride and methyl migrations⁷ followed by C-15 (α) proton elimination to furnish the intermediate 9. The OH group at C-6 is now favourably oriented which is then eliminated as a molecule of water with the concomitant methyl migration and C-10 (α) proton elimination resulting in the formation of the diene (6) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The epoxide (1) on treatment with BF_3 -etherate in anhydrous benzene furnished a single hydrocarbon which was identical in all respects with the non-conjugated diene (6).

The epoxide (1) formed the intermediate ion-pair (10) with BF_3 -etherate in a cage of non-polar solvent⁸ like benzene. The formation of a classical carbocation⁹ in 10 can thus be assumed which, in turn, is converted into the intermediate complex (11) by a series of hydride and methyl migrations⁷. Departure of HOBF_3 from 11 followed by concerted C-5 (β) methyl migration and C-10 (α) proton elimination finally results in the formation of the diene (6) as shown in the Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

The molecular rearrangements of D : A-friedelan- $3\beta,4\beta$ -epoxide⁶ with BF_3 -etherate corroborated the abovesaid mechanistic interpretation.

Interaction between the epoxide (1) and aqueous perchloric acid in THF furnished an unsaturated alcohol (12) along with the unchanged starting epoxide (1). In the nmr spectrum of the alcohol (12), an ill-defined multiplet (1H) at δ 4.06 might be represented by the $\text{C}_7\text{-}\beta$ proton and the olefinic proton at C-15 appeared as a pair of doublets (1H) centered around δ 5.88 (J 4 Hz, 6 Hz).

In acid medium the protonated epoxide (7) undergoes $\text{C}_6\text{-O}$ (α) bond cleavage followed by backbone rearrangement⁷ leading to 12. Compound 12 underwent smooth acetylation with a mixture of acetic anhydride and pyridine to furnish the corresponding acetate (13).

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. The petroleum ether used had b.p. 60–80° unless otherwise stated. Optical rotations were measured in chloroform. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Jeol Fx-100 (100 MHz) instrument using TMS as the internal standard unless stated otherwise.

Epi-putranjivol (2) was prepared by the standard method³.

Isoputranjivene (4) from epi-putranjivol (2): A mixture of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (5 g), epi-putranjivol (2 g) and pyridine (50 ml) was allowed to stand for 112 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, extracted with ether and the ether layer on usual work up afforded the crude tosyl derivative (2 g) to which lithium aluminium hydride (3 g) was added to the THF (300 ml) solution of the same. Further work up in usual procedure followed by crystallisation from acetone and chloroform gave isoputranjivene (4), m.p. 166–68° (Found: C, 87.92; H, 12.02. C₃₀H₅₀ requires: C, 87.80; H, 12.20%); [α]_D –18°; ν_{\max} 1454 and 1360 (*gem*-dimethyl) and 835 cm⁻¹ (olefinic double bond); *m/z* 410 (M⁺, 18%), 395 [(M–CH₃)⁺, 21%], 231 (21%), 218 (100%) and 177 (36%).

Epoxidation of isoputranjivene (4): *m*-Chloroperbenzoic acid (2.50 g) in chloroform (50 ml) was added with stirring to a solution of isoputranjivene (4; 2 g) in chloroform (50 ml) at 0°. The complete consumption of the starting material was monitored by tlc on silica gel and the reaction was complete within 8 h. Usual work up furnished a semi-solid mass (1.98 g) which was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (60 g).

D: A-Friedoolean-6 α ,7 α -epoxide (1): Elution of the above column with a mixture of petroleum ether-benzene (19:1) afforded colourless crystals (ca. 1.52 g), m.p. 182–86°, which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and acetone yielded compound 1 (60%), m.p. 185–88° (Found: C, 84.52; H, 11.77. C₃₀H₅₀O requires: C, 84.50; H, 11.74%); [α]_D –6.28°; ν_{\max} 1440 and 1380 (*gem*-dimethyl), 880 and 800 cm⁻¹ (epoxy function); *m/z* 426 (M⁺, 6%), 411 [(M–CH₃)⁺, 36%], 408 [(M–H₂O)⁺, 24%], 393 (44%), 302 (12%), 273 (28%), 232 (6%), 205 (42%), 191 (35%), 175 (44%), 123 (100%) and 69 (85%).

D: A-Friedoolean 6 β ,7 β -epoxide (5): Further elution of the above chromatogram with petroleum ether-benzene (9:1) yielded a solid (0.42 g), m.p. 180–84°, which was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and acetone to furnish the epoxide (5), m.p. 182–84° (Found: C, 84.21; H, 11.80. C₃₀H₅₀O requires: C, 84.50; H, 11.74%); [α]_D +34.07°; ν_{\max} 1470 and 1390 (*gem*-dimethyl), 890 and 810 cm⁻¹ (epoxy function); *m/z* 426 (M⁺, 4%), 411 [(M–CH₃)⁺, 38%], 408 [(M–H₂O)⁺, 25%], 393 (40%), 302 (11%), 273 (30%), 232 (6%),

205 (42%), 191 (38%), 175 (48%), 123 (100%) and 69 (86%).

Rearrangement of the epoxide (1) with hydrogen chloride: Dry HCl gas was passed through the chloroform (50 ml) solution of the epoxide (1; 0.12 g) for 3 h at room temperature. Usual work up furnished a solid (0.10 g) which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and acetone yielded the diene (6; 90%), m.p. 148–50° (Found: C, 88.46; H, 11.62. C₃₀H₄₈ requires: C, 88.33; H, 11.77%); [α]_D +7.14°; λ_{\max} 209.2 nm (absence of any conjugated diene system); ν_{\max} 1440 and 1360 (*gem*-dimethyl), 840 cm⁻¹ (trisubstituted double bond).

Rearrangement of the epoxide (1) with boron trifluoride etherate: A solution of the epoxide (1; 0.20 g) in dry benzene (10 ml) was treated with freshly distilled BF₃-etherate (0.2 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. Usual work up afforded a crude solid (0.18 g) which was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and acetone to give the diene (6, 88%), m.p. 146–50°, [α]_D +6.84°, identical (mixed m.p., co-tlc and ir) with the diene obtained by the action of dry HCl gas on the epoxide (1).

Reaction of the epoxide (1) with aqueous perchloric acid: Aqueous perchloric acid (4 ml; 3 N) was treated with a solution of the epoxide (1; 0.2 g) in THF (2.5 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 8 h at room temperature. Usual work up furnished a crude mass (0.2 g) which was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (20 g).

Compound 14-en-7 α -ol (12): Further elution of the above column with a mixture of petroleum ether-benzene (4:1) furnished a solid (0.12 g) which on crystallisation from CHCl₃-MeOH gave 12 (60%), m.p. 196–98° (Found: C, 84.70; H, 11.72. C₃₀H₅₀O requires: C, 84.50; H, 11.77%); [α]_D +66.66°; *m/z* 426 (M⁺, 32%), 408 [(M–H₂O)⁺, 38%], 284 (100%), 269 (88%), 189 (42%) and 124 (18%).

Compound 14-en-7 α -acetate (13): The above mono-alcohol (12; 0.12 g) was acetylated in the usual manner with Ac₂O (1.2 ml) and pyridine (1.2 ml) to afford the corresponding acetate (0.10 g, 83%), which on crystallisation from CHCl₃-MeOH furnished the acetate (13), m.p. 156–58° (Found: C, 82.21; H, 11.09. C₃₂H₅₂O₂ requires: C, 82.05; H, 11.11%); [α]_D +9.52°; *m/z* 468 [(M⁺), 8%], 408 393, 284, 269, 204 and 124.

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